

Two Concepts of Educational Freedom

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This article is intended to challenge one common conception of educational freedom, and to propose an alternative conception.¹ Even if we rarely employ the *terminology* of freedom, the concepts of and concerns about educational freedom are highly relevant to the contemporary educational context; for example, debates regarding formal and informal education often portray informal learning contexts as inherently freer — and therefore better — than formal ones. Even without being explicitly stated, beliefs about freedom inform many policy debates, such as those regarding student-directed online learning, the increasing prevalence of the homeschooling movement, and the increasing dominance of rules and regulations both inside and beyond the classroom. Accordingly, it is important to carefully consider what conception of educational freedom may be most fruitful for those engaged in such discussions.

The view that I want to challenge sees educational freedom as the mere absence of constraints. This approach involves an unhelpful confusion regarding the concept of educational freedom and an inaccurate, binary view of the relationship between freedom and constraint. In contrast to the view that freedom and constraint are opposed to one another, so that one increases exactly as the other decreases, the view that I advocate in this article recognizes that freedom and constraint are in fact inseparably linked to one another. Freedom is not a simplistic absence of constraints, but rather is determined by the scope of action afforded by one's social setting. My argument in this article is that, while the former approach to educational freedom dominates educational debates today, the latter approach leads to more nuanced and productive discussions in important areas of policy and practice.

In order to clarify the two approaches to educational freedom just mentioned, I first use the contrasting lenses of two educational theorists whose work was most widely read in the 1960s and '70s, a historical period deeply invested in promoting individual freedom and challenging traditional authority and institutions, both within education and in society more broadly. My purpose in discussing these two educators is *not* to evaluate them in themselves; that work has been done repeatedly. Rather, I use them to exemplify two contrasting conceptions of educational freedom. I then explain the concepts of “agency” and “structure,” which I borrow from Anthony Giddens' structuration theory. With these concepts in mind, I develop my own agency-based conception of freedom. Finally, I demonstrate the usefulness of this alternative view of freedom by applying it to the educational debates mentioned in this introduction.

1. A. S. Neill and Educational Freedom

The first approach to educational freedom is exemplified by the work of A. S. Neill, who put into practice the principle of student freedom more thoroughly than any other educator during his many decades as founder and headmaster of Summerhill, a residential (i.e., boarding) school in Suffolk, England. Summerhill's most frequently discussed features, and those most relevant to understanding Neill's view of educational freedom, were self-government and non-compulsory lessons.² Self-government was carried out via weekly meetings of the entire Summerhill community to discuss matters of communal concern. At these meetings, anyone could raise an issue for the community to discuss, and anyone could offer his or her view on the issue being discussed. When the time came to vote, each person had one vote, regardless of age or rank: as Neill said, "My [i.e., the headmaster's] vote carries the same weight as that of a seven-year-old" (16). However, the school did not make *all* decisions by communal vote — only those concerning matters such as rules, inter-personal conflicts, and punishments. Neill or the staff decided about accepting new students and hiring new teachers, oversaw finances and purchases, and addressed food and safety concerns without consulting the children (18). As for lessons, students had "freedom to go to lessons or stay away, freedom to play for days or weeks or years if necessary" (3). Teachers were not allowed to compel students to attend lessons, nor were other students supposed to compel their fellows to stay away from lessons (though Neill admitted that this sometimes happened). Overall, Neill boasted that Summerhill School had "[s]elf-government for the pupils and staff, freedom to go to lessons or stay away, freedom to play for days or weeks or years if necessary, freedom from any indoctrination whether religious or moral or political, freedom from character moulding" (3).

To illustrate the kind of freedom found at Summerhill, consider Neill's story of a young student, Winifred, who came to Summerhill at age thirteen. At first, she rejoiced when she found out she was no longer required to go to lessons or study any subject she did not want to. However, a few weeks later she grew bored and asked Neill to teach her something. He asked what she wanted to learn, but she said she didn't know. Several months later she asked him to help her pass the college entrance exams. He concludes the anecdote with this self-satisfied report: "Every morning she worked with me and other teachers, and she worked well. She confided that the subjects did not interest her much, but the aim *did* interest her. Winifred found herself by being allowed to be herself" (Neill 126). Even in this brief anecdote, we can see the problem with Neill's view of freedom as the absence of constraints: it seems just as likely that Winifred found, not herself, but the only conceivable alternative to boredom. Whether Neill's goal was to help Winifred discover what she truly wanted to learn, or to push back against her over-reliance on adults to tell her what to do and to keep her entertained, his *laissez faire* approach failed in its intent. I return to the case of Winifred in a later section, and suggest how Neill might have acted differently toward her if he had had a more nuanced conception of educational freedom.

Neill exhibits the first conception of freedom, freedom as the absence of constraints, throughout his account of the Summerhill approach to education. In this view, children

are free when they can do what they want without being constrained by society. In Neill's own words, "Freedom means doing what you like, so long as you don't interfere with the freedom of others. The result is self-discipline" (44). Although Neill designed Summerhill in order to remove any and all societal constraints so that children could be truly free, he downplayed at least four key ways in which society necessarily does influence the individual.

First, caregivers limit children's self-regulation for the sake of safety, not only for themselves and for the children under their care, but also for the safety of others (see Neill 36 and Barrett). *Second*, even at Summerhill, numerous decisions that affected the daily lives of the children were not resolved by the whole community (in accordance with Neill's concept of self-government), but by Neill or another member of the staff — for example, the food to be served at meals, the hiring and firing of staff, bedroom arrangements, and textbooks. Neill dismisses these non-democratic decisions: "None of these factors comes into self-government. Nor do the pupils want them to. Self-government to them means dealing with situations that arise in their communal life" (18). Of course, one might wonder whether the children were *really* indifferent about these matters, or might have cared about them had they been given the chance to be involved in the decision. But the more important point is that Neill downplayed the extent to which such decisions shaped the children's lives and choices. *Third*, even without explicit coercion, children are persuaded toward or away from certain actions by observing and interacting with both their peers and the adults in their community. For example, although the adults at Summerhill were not supposed to force children to attend lessons, children themselves could and did keep one another away from lessons (129). Neill bemoaned this occurrence, but in fact it was inevitable. And *fourth*, it is not only other *individuals* that exert influence over the individuals with whom they interact; societal *structures* do so, as well. A prime example of this is the General Meetings that enabled Summerhill to be a self-governing community. (I elaborate on the structural nature of self-government in a later section of this article.)

To summarize, Neill's conception of freedom failed to recognize that ignorance of available options can significantly hamper students' ability to choose what they truly want to learn, and that merely *telling* them to be independent is insufficient for helping them escape over-dependence on adult authority. Consequently, he did not see the need for either exposing students to a variety of areas of learning or guiding them in choosing what and how to learn. Moreover, his account of free education at Summerhill downplays the role of social structures and influences in shaping the choices of even those individuals who are relatively "free" by Neill's own definition (that is, who are neither required to do things they do not want to do, nor prevented from doing whatever they do want to, except under certain special circumstances). For all these reasons, if our standard is the total absence of constraints, then educational freedom is completely unattainable.

2. Ivan Illich and Educational Freedom

We can begin to see the alternative approach that I propose, viewing educational freedom not as the absence of constraints but as the scope for action, in the work of Ivan Illich, a lapsed Catholic priest who was heavily involved throughout the 1970s in the influential Center for Intercultural Documentation (Centro Intercultural de Documentación) at Cuernavaca, Mexico. Like Neill, Illich also critiqued schooling, calling it “the age-specific, teacher-related process requiring full-time attendance at an obligatory curriculum” (26). Yet Illich’s conception of freedom is subtly but crucially different from Neill’s.

For Illich, the primary characteristic of unfree learners is *dependency* (2). Specifically, unfree learners are dependent on *teachers* for their learning (that is, they are unable to *learn* without being *taught*), and they are dependent on *schools* for access to instruction. It is important to note here that Illich does not believe anyone *actually* is incapable of untaught learning — on the contrary, he frequently emphasizes that most learning does *not* require direct, planned instruction. In fact, he writes, “learning is the human activity which least needs manipulation by others. Most learning is not the result of instruction. It is rather the result of unhampered participation in a meaningful setting” (39). Schools do not change the fundamental nature of human learning, but they do change learners’ *views* of human learning. “Most people learn best by being ‘with it’, yet school makes them identify their personal, cognitive growth with elaborate planning and manipulation” (39). Thus, unfree learners *could* learn on their own — but they don’t realize this. They *expect* to be unable to learn without teaching, and so they never attempt to do otherwise. Thus, their view of themselves as dependent learners becomes a self-fulfilling prophecy.

If unfree learners are dependent on institutions and teachers to package and deliver their learning, then free learners are the opposite: independent. This need not mean that they never make use of formal instruction and even institutions that look a lot like traditional schools. But when they do, they do so for their own purposes, not for those determined by others; in other words, they “tak[e] control of their own learning” (Illich 8). Free, independent learners are characterized by “action, participation, and self-help” (64) as well as “autonomy [and] motivation” (104). If a free learner wants to learn something, she is able to set her own learning goals (perhaps with the help of a friend or teacher), to seek out the most effective means *for herself* (which may differ from what is most effective for a different learner), and to actively pursue her goals (again, possibly in conjunction with a role model or peers). She does not have to be constantly reminded to complete her learning tasks, nor must she be externally rewarded for doing so. She is motivated by purposes of her own.

The difference between Illich’s conception of free learners and Neill’s is subtle, but crucial. If freedom is simply the absence of constraints, then any societal constraint — even the gentlest suggestion or influence — means the end of freedom. But if freedom

means independence, then societal structures and even constraints do not destroy freedom. Rather, these structures raise questions such as ‘*What do these structures enable students to do?*’ and ‘*How are students able to act by means of these structures, but not in total dependence on them?*’ As these questions indicate, Illich is fully aware that even free learners need access to resources; they cannot pursue their own, self-generated learning goals in a vacuum. Illich identifies four types of resources that are necessary for learning:

Someone who wants to learn knows that he needs both information and critical response to its use from somebody else. Information can be stored in *things* and in *persons*.... Criticism can also come from two directions: from *peers* or from *elders*, that is, from fellow learners whose immediate interests match mine, or from those who will grant me a share in their superior experience. (78)

So learners need some way to access educational objects, role models and instructors, peers with mutual interests, and elders with wisdom to share. Despite this fairly thorough account of the *positive* resources needed for self-education, the problem of providing access to such resources remains. It is not sufficient for learners to stumble upon the necessary resources in a haphazard fashion (though even that would be better than being unable to access them at all). Rather, to facilitate learning, we need some sort of structure for connecting learners with these different types of resources for learning; in fact, we may even need institutions for doing so. But Illich believes that obligatory, age-graded, curriculum-oriented schools engender the exact opposite of independent, autonomous learning. Clearly, we need some vision of what a freedom-promoting institution would look like.³

Illich provides a pair of terms for distinguishing between institutions that promote freedom and those that restrict or undermine it; freedom-promoting institutions are “convivial,” and freedom-restricting institutions are “manipulative” (53). Convivial institutions “exist to be used rather than to produce something” (55), while manipulative institutions are just the opposite. The “product” created by unfree institutions may be a physical object or a service such as schooling or healthcare (which Illich often calls “treatments”). But whatever they produce, these institutions exist to produce more of it, whether or not anyone actually desires those products. Then, in order to justify their existence, manipulative institutions have to create societal or psychological demand for their products; thus, “much of the elaboration and expense is concerned with convincing consumers that they cannot live without the product or the treatment offered by the institution” (55). Manipulative institutions may even generate rules that “call for unwilling consumption or participation” (55). In contrast, “[t]he rules which govern institutions for use [that is, convivial institutions] have mainly the purpose of avoiding abuses which would frustrate their general accessibility” (55). This regulation “sets limits to their use” (55); it never forces people to use the institution if they do not want to. Overall, the key distinction is that convivial (i.e., freedom-promoting) institutions are used *willingly* while manipulative (i.e., freedom-restricting) institutions are not.

Illich further distinguishes between institutions that are more like “funnels” and those that are more like “webs” (vii). A funnel corrals all learners into one predetermined learning path, regardless of individual learners’ needs and desires. A web, on the other hand, allows for a multitude of diverse learning moments — diverse both across different learners and within one learner’s lifetime. The goal of a web is “the autonomous assembly of resources under the personal control of each learner” (70); free, web-like institutions “develop ... independence and learning” (77). In contrast, the goal of a funnel is to deliver “packages” of learning to its “clients” (i.e., students); thus, manipulative, funnel-like institutions develop “bureaucracy and teaching” (77).⁴ Even with these distinctions, however, a web is still a structure, and so it still places constraints on educational actions. But these constraints are qualitatively different from the constraints imposed by a funnel: a web opens up far more possibilities than a funnel does.

As we continue to extend Illich’s theory, we may find it useful to think of the structures of educational possibilities (such as funnels and webs) as lying on a spectrum rather than as being opposed to one another. At one end is the strictest form of funnel, a one-size-supposedly-fits-all “package” of educational “treatment.” A slightly more flexible structure offers a choice among a limited set of “packages,” such as between regular, vocational, or college-preparatory high school programs. Such a structure is less like a web, in Illich’s sense, and more like a set of funnels (i.e., there is only one choice to be made, and that choice is limited to a highly restricted number of options). Illich’s web probably lies even further along the spectrum, offering not few but many possible options and combinations of options. And at the furthest extreme from the single funnel (and pushing the physical metaphor to its limit), we might think of educators as inviting students to make their own way through an open terrain. Yet even this is not the kind of unconstrained “freedom” advocated by Neill; students are still influenced and constrained by the very nature of what they are learning, as well as by the very invitation to pursue exploration itself. Furthermore, the point along this spectrum that represents a truly freedom-promoting structure largely depends on the characteristics of individual students. Finally, we must remember that for Illich freedom-promoting structures are identified not only by whether they are more like funnels or more like webs, but also by whether the decision concerning which of many possible paths to take remains in the hands of the learner herself.

To summarize, Neill and Illich both criticize the traditional approach to schooling as detrimental to students’ freedom. However, their proposed solutions do differ, and those differences are significant for illuminating a crucial problem in contemporary discussions of freedom and constraint in education. Neill holds that the only way to preserve students’ freedom is to remove all societal constraints, letting each individual develop as she chooses. Yet this is neither sociologically feasible nor educationally desirable. Illich, on the other hand, recognizes that structure and constraint are unavoidable; moreover, certain structures are actually *necessary* for promoting true educational freedom. He offers two related markers of freedom-promoting structures: they keep control in the hands of the user, and they support *many* possible paths rather than only one. Illich’s conception of educational freedom as “independent use of web-like structures” (78)

redirects our focus toward a consideration of the *kinds* of structures that make free learning possible.

Yet the key difference between Illich's view of educational freedom and Neill's is still not clear. I therefore believe that we can and must go further than Illich did in moving away from thinking of educational freedom as the mere lack of constraints. In the next section, I use the terminology of structuration theory — in particular, the concepts of “agency” and “structure” — to develop a more useful conception of educational freedom in which freedom becomes the positive scope for action, action that is always necessarily dependent on structures and even constraints.

3. Freedom as Agency

Having illustrated two contrasting views of students' freedom, I now propose a vocabulary that enables us to conceptualize the relationship between educational freedom and structural constraints in a non-dichotomous way. I suggest that, rather than framing the problem in terms of freedom *versus* constraint, we may more fruitfully conceive of agency *within* structure. But in order to make the case for this conceptual shift, I must explain what I mean by “agency” and “structure.” The explanation of these terms that I give here draws on the structuration theory of Anthony Giddens. Giddens developed structuration theory as a response to the dualism found in mid-twentieth-century social theory, in which human agency was pitted against rigid, quasi-deterministic social structures. Giddens sought to move beyond this dichotomy and present a unified theory in which agency and structure were each inseparable parts of the other.⁵

Despite the undeniable influence of Giddens' theory of structuration on the social theory of the late twentieth and early twenty-first theory, structuration theory has had little impact on either the sociology or the philosophy of education. Chris Shilling calls for sociologists of education to give “serious attention” (84) to structuration theory, yet almost two decades later Laura Day Ashley notes that “[c]ompared with other fields ... Giddens' structuration theory appears to be under-used in educational research” (338). If structuration theory is “under-used” in *empirical* research on education, it has had practically no impact on *theoretical* inquiries into education. Accordingly, I propose a new use of structuration theory: I use it not to inform the empirical study of educational situations, but to frame the philosophical conceptualization of educational freedom. Specifically, I suggest that we think of the agency-structure dualism found in structuration theory as analogous to the freedom-constraint dualism I have been discussing so far in this paper. Seen in this light, Giddens' new conceptualizations of agency, structure, and the relationship between them point towards a more productive way of thinking about educational freedom.

In structuration theory, *agency* is the capability of individuals to do things, rather than to have things done to them — to act of and for themselves in the world. In Giddens' words, “Agency refers to doing” (10). Someone who has agency — an *agent* — is not necessarily unconstrained; rather, she is the efficient cause of her own actions, whatever other influences, including constraints, may have contributed to those actions. The

contrast at the heart of talk about agency is *not* between constraint and lack of constraint, but between activity and passivity.

Agency is intimately related to power. Giddens expresses the relationship between the two as follows:

To be able to ‘act otherwise’ means being able to intervene in the world, or to refrain from such intervention, with the effect of influencing a specific process or state of affairs. This presumes that to be an agent is to be able to deploy (chronically, in the flow of daily life) a range of causal powers, including that of influencing those deployed by others. Action depends upon the capability of the individual to ‘make a difference’ to a pre-existing state of affairs or course of events. (14)

Thus, power is simply the ability to act in the world. If someone has agency, she also has power, and vice versa. This applies even to those who are typically perceived as being “subordinate” or even “oppressed”:

We should not conceive of the structures of domination built into social institutions as in some way grinding out ‘docile bodies’ who behave like the automata suggested by objectivist social science.... [A]ll forms of dependence offer some resources whereby those who are subordinate can influence the activities of their superiors. (16)

In other words, no human, group of humans, or social structure is able to render another human or group of humans completely powerless. Some structures do limit agency more than others, a point I elaborate on below. We do well to attend to the degree to which various structures, including schools and educational policies, curb the ability of particular humans to exercise their agency. But even the most limiting structure imaginable cannot turn a human being into a powerless non-agent.⁶

Once we grasp this conception of agency, i.e., not as total autonomy and independence from social influence, but as the ability to act of oneself in the world, we are well positioned to understand structure as well. Giddens defines structure as made up of “[r]ules and resources” (377). This broad definition includes not only the formalized institutions that are Illich’s focus but also cultural norms, patterns of behavior, ways of speaking, and so on. Structure is not an independent force that influences or even determines human behavior; rather, human action itself constantly reproduces or alters structure. At the same time, structure makes human acts what they are. As Giddens insists, “[s]tructure is not to be equated with constraint but is always both constraining and enabling” (25). In other words, in the absence of structure, it would be impossible for humans to exercise agency.

It is relatively easy to see how *resources* can be enabling: wealth, prestige, political office, and other physical and social resources *are* resources precisely because they widen the scope of action for those who possess them. *Rules*, on the other hand, are often

thought of as constraints on the possibility of free action. Yet rules, which Giddens describes as “techniques or generalizable procedures applied to the enactment/reproduction of social practices” (21), show us how to carry out particular acts in the first place; they constitute those acts as meaningful within a given social setting. Thus, rules as well as resources are necessary for enabling humans to act with agency. The rules and resources of a particular social structure do not only set limits on the scope of human action; they also make it possible for that action to occur. Social structures are like train tracks: Trains have to go wherever the tracks go, but the tracks make it possible for trains to go anywhere in the first place. So train tracks enable the movement of the train *by* constraining it. Likewise, by constraining human action, structures enable agents’ actions.

Thinking in terms of agency and structure, as I have explained them here, leads us to view the matter of educational freedom in a more balanced, nuanced way. We can recognize the ways students have agentive control over their actions, even in the most restrictive educational settings — and the ways even the most restrictive educational settings provide students with rules and resources for action, even while significantly constraining that action. Yet the shift to the concepts of agency and structure that I propose does not preclude critical evaluation of educational rules and regulations; on the contrary, it offers a more coherent criterion for identifying overly constraining educational structures and policies.

All structures, as I have explained them here, both enable and constrain. Nevertheless, we can still evaluate different structures as *relatively* more agency-enabling or agency-constraining. Accordingly, we can judge different structures with respect to their relationship to human agency.⁷ Agency-friendly structures are *particularly* important for education, because agency must be *developed*: children learn how to exercise their agency through participation in educational structures that support their growing abilities to control their own learning.

I suggest that we reconceptualize educational freedom, not as the simple absence of constraints (and thus something that one either does or does not have), but as the relative scope for human agency provided by one’s social contexts. We could think of this in terms of the *breadth* and *depth* of agency: the range of different things one is able to do, and how meaningful or significant one perceives those things to be. Or, in keeping with the idea, explained above, that structural conditions are necessary for human action, we might look at both the *flexibility of rules* and *access to resources*: who decides the rules, who is able to change them, and how easily; who has certain resources, how easily they are obtained, and how easily they change hands. Undergirding such inquiries is the idea that it is not primarily the *amount* of constraint that matters, but rather its *nature*; in other words, the difference between freedom-promoting and freedom-restricting structures is qualitative, not quantitative.

4. Illustrations of Freedom-as-Agency

To demonstrate the usefulness of my proposed agency-based conception of freedom, I first revisit Neill's account of Summerhill. I then briefly discuss the three contemporary educational debates mentioned in the introduction to this article (student-directed online learning, the increasing prevalence of homeschooling, and the increasing dominance of rules and regulations) in order to show how the conception of freedom-as-agency brings greater clarity to these debates and opens up new directions for discussion.

As I have already mentioned, Neill failed to recognize the structures that *did* exist at Summerhill. To illustrate this, I will look at two contrasting examples of structure and constraint at Summerhill: the issue of self-government and the General Meeting, and Neill's interaction with Winifred. I argue that the structures of self-government were, in fact, necessary for promoting the genuine freedom experienced at Summerhill; in contrast, in the case of Winifred, it was not structure, but the *lack* of structure, that truly constrained her educational freedom.

The most obvious example of structure at Summerhill was the school's policy of self-government, embodied in the weekly General Meeting. We can recognize the General Meeting as a structure — and a freedom-promoting one at that — by analyzing its rules and resources. The *resources* provided by the General Meeting included a time and place for the entire community to come together, the mechanisms for raising and addressing grievances or other matters of communal concern, and the policy of one vote per person. The *rules* of the General Meeting were both explicit (e.g., “each person gets exactly one vote, regardless of age or status”) and implicit (e.g., “it is better to persuade others by reasonable arguments than by force or authority”). These rules sanctioned certain types of behavior and not others (e.g., bringing up a bully at the meeting was a more accepted way of dealing with him than exacting personal vengeance); they also constituted the meanings of certain acts (e.g., the act of voting had no meaning if there was no meeting in which to vote, and the act of breaking someone else's private property had no meaning if there was no government to back up the notion that property could be private and had value [see Neill 31]).

Clearly, self-government and the General Meeting were enabling: they allowed laws to be made, cases to be heard, and punishments for deviant behavior to be decided by the community itself. Less clearly, but just as certainly, this structure was also constraining. If one wanted to bring an issue before the community, one had to do it at the time and place of the General Meeting, not at some other time or place. This very *constraint* was what *enabled* all members of the community to come together and participate in decision-making. In addition, as Neill acknowledged, under self-government dissenting minorities are constrained to accept the majority decision (21). It is difficult to see how this constraint is also enabling, but the rule of the majority is inherent in the very nature of democracy. To do away with self-government in the interest of minority rights would be

even more constraining, as the children learned during the few occasions of total anarchy at Summerhill. The discussions and votes that took place at General Meetings lent such legitimacy to the community's decisions that, in general, minorities usually accepted the will of the majority without protest. In these ways, then, Neill's practice was better than his theory (as in many other instances as well): although he explicitly considered freedom to be opposed to *all* forms of societal constraint, he permitted, and even encouraged, self-government because he valued the opportunities for freedom — understood as agency — that it afforded.

The need for certain structures and even constraints in order to promote educational freedom can be seen most clearly in the story of Winifred, who asked Neill to “teach her something.” When she did not know what she wanted to learn, Neill refused to offer any guidance or suggestions at all. So she chose to study for the university entrance exams, not because she found the subjects interesting, but because she considered them better than the boredom she felt when she had nothing to study. As Neill tells it, this is a laudable example of the lack of constraint at Summerhill. Winifred was not required to take certain subjects, as she would have been at another school; in fact, she was not even constrained by the slightest *suggestion* from Neill of a possible course of action. But I would suggest that she was effectively limited to the choices she *perceived* to be available to her at Summerhill — boredom or the university entrance subjects. Although Neill's refusal to guide her in discovering what she wanted to learn might appear to increase her freedom, in reality it constrained her to choose from the subjects of which she already had some awareness. A few thoughtful suggestions from Neill, while in one sense constraining her (by influencing her decision), would have also enabled her to choose from a wider range of possibilities than a thirteen-year-old could be expected to know about on her own.

Of course, it is possible that Neill's true intent was not for Winifred to find something genuinely interesting to learn. Instead, he may have been trying to wean her from her over-dependence (as he perceived it) on adults for direction and entertainment. If this interpretation of Neill's motives is correct, then the fact that Winifred made her choice without any input from Neill does indeed *look* like success. But in fact, Winifred was still almost entirely dependent on adult influences: she chose a highly conventional learning goal (again, most likely because she knew of few other options), and once she made her choice, there is every indication that she pursued it in a highly conventional way. Thus, whether Neill was trying to help her find what she truly wanted to learn or to make her less dependent on adult authority, his unyielding refusal to influence her in any way ultimately undermined his educational goal.

Furthermore, in coming to Neill, Winifred was *already displaying* her agency in seeking out an education for herself. Neill would not have harmed her agency by offering guidance; on the contrary, by refusing to give her the help she asked for, he further restricted her ability to act. As Winifred saw the situation, she had two educational options: she could either get Neill's help in finding something interesting to learn, or pursue the only learning possibility she herself knew about (the university entrance subjects), which she admitted “did not interest her much” (Neill 126). Of these options,

she preferred the former; thus, when Neill refused to help her, he closed off the educational choice *she herself had made*. To be sure, Winifred's agency was already curtailed by her limited knowledge about what and how she could learn — but that is precisely why she needed guidance from Neill. Such guidance would have extended, not restricted, her agency by offering her an even wider range of options from which to choose.⁸

The alternative conception of freedom that I advocate also sheds light on contemporary educational debates, such as discussions of formal and informal learning contexts. Understanding freedom as agency guards us against an overly simplistic association of formality with constraint and structure, and informality with freedom and lack of structure. Quite the contrary, both agency and structure can be found in dynamic interaction within *every* learning context, regardless of where that context falls on the formal-informal spectrum. More specifically, the agency-within-structure conception of educational freedom enables us to recognize *two* claims: first, that informal, implicit structures (such as those found in families) are indeed structures, composed of rules and resources that shape human action; and second, that formal structures (such as those found in classrooms) can still promote learners' agency, often more effectively than informal structures can. The question is not, '*Which learning contexts provide structure, and which ones provide agency?*' Rather, we should be asking, '*How does the interplay of structure and agency manifest itself in various learning contexts, and what structures (both formal and informal) best promote learners' agency within those diverse contexts?*' To illustrate these points, I use the agency-within-structure lens to briefly analyze four learning contexts: two relatively informal, and two relatively formal.

First, online learning. In many ways, resources like Kahn Academy and MIT OpenCourseWare are the latest iteration of the same student-directed learning movement that Illich, Neill, and even John Dewey have been part of. The advocates of online learning frequently point out that these resources enable students to exercise educational agency. Online learning resources do give students more control in certain areas than traditional schools do. However, these resources are still quite structured; they present students with a highly organized array of learning materials, often fairly linear in progression, precisely in order to allow students to learn without constant direction from a teacher. Thus, the freedom that these resources offer students is agency-within-structure. At the same time, online learning resources do also constrain students' access to other important types of learning, such as face-to-face interaction and open-ended feedback. As with all structures, the trade-off in enabling certain actions is constraining others.

Similar types of constraints and possibilities are evident in a second area of debate, homeschooling. A key characteristic of present-day homeschooling is the apparent tension between parents' rights to educate their children as they choose, free from state interference, and children's rights to a decent education, whatever their parents' means and desires. An adequate treatment of how the conception of freedom-as-agency provides greater clarity to this thorny issue will have to wait for future work. For now, I merely wish to point out that being educated at home — rather than at school — is itself a

particular structure. Homeschooling does limit students in certain ways, as opponents point out. For example, homeschooled students may have more limited opportunities to interact with other children from diverse backgrounds. At the same time, homeschooling also allows students to meet community members of *all* ages and backgrounds. Furthermore, much like student-directed online learning, homeschooling enables students to explore and find out how *they* learn best, rather than requiring them to follow the school schedule and teaching methods. In this respect, at least, the structure of homeschooling may be much more freedom-enabling than that of traditional schooling.

Both online learning and homeschooling are often seen as less formal learning contexts than classroom-based instruction. But the dynamic of agency-within-structure also manifests itself in traditional classrooms. Consider the portion of the classroom day given to reading instruction and practice. It might seem that the literacy period is necessarily formal, structured, and constraining; how else can teachers ensure that all their students learn to read? But in fact it is possible to deliberately build student choice and agency into the very process of learning to read, even in a traditional classroom setting. For example, the Daily 5, a well-known way of structuring literacy periods in the elementary grades, seeks to give students greater choice and independence (i.e., agency) in how they spend their literacy time, while maintaining high expectations regarding appropriate behavior during that time. In order to achieve these goals, the Daily 5 presents students with highly structured choices regarding what, when, where, and how they complete the required literacy tasks. In particular, students choose the order in which they complete five literacy tasks: Read to Self, Work on Writing, Read to Someone, Listen to Reading, and Word Work (i.e., spelling practice). The creators of the Daily 5 report,

Even though [the literacy tasks] are non-negotiable, students enjoy the freedom to choose the order in which they will participate in each activity.... Choice is one of the key reasons that students love the Daily 5, develop the habits of readers, and greatly improve their reading. (Boushey and Moser 16)

It would be a mistake, both theoretically and pedagogically, to see this methodology as exhibiting structure (and hence lack of choice) in some areas, and freedom (and hence lack of structure) in others. Rather, the structure itself — the clearly specified options for what to do and how to do it — makes it possible for students to make meaningful choices regarding how they spend their literacy time. The absence of the Daily 5 structure would lead to *less* freedom, not more. By giving students structured agency, the Daily 5 methodology ensures both that they have ample opportunities to develop as readers and writers *and* that they can exercise their agency in doing so.

Finally, although this article has focused on students, my proposed conception of freedom-as-agency also applies to teachers. One of the biggest educational policy debates today has to do with regulation. The rhetoric of this debate often displays the dichotomy between freedom and constraint, particularly in arguments made by opponents of regulation. But shifting perspective to focus on agency-within-structure opens up new

possibilities for debating both the costs and the benefits of regulation. We can still critique certain regulations as overly constraining by pointing to the ways they limit teachers' agency in making pedagogical choices that are appropriate for their own students. At the same time, we can also recognize what regulations *enable* teachers to do. For example, increased standardization allows teachers to coordinate their instruction with teachers in other grades and even other districts.

One final note in passing: the conception of freedom-as-agency that I advocate here has no inherent predisposition toward either libertarian or interventionist policies and practices. In each of the debates outlined above, and in countless others, the exact same educational structure might be freedom-promoting in one situation or for one student or group of students, and freedom-restricting for another. As just one example, consider Lisa Delpit's critique of "child-centered, whole language, and process approaches" to teaching writing that fail to give children from non-White, non-middle class backgrounds the tools needed to succeed in a society that will inevitably judge them on the basis of their "product" and their mastery of the codes of power (Delpit 31). In such a context, more explicit instruction is in fact more empowering — though, as Delpit makes sure to point out, it must not undermine respect for the students' own knowledge and agency, nor divorce their writing practice from "real audiences and real purposes" (33). By directing our focus to what educational structures enable particular students to *do*, the conception of freedom-as-agency highlights the merits of Delpit's critique and of her proposed solutions.

5. Conclusion

In this article I have contrasted two approaches to educational freedom. One views freedom as the mere absence of constraints, such that any increase in constraints necessarily entails a decrease in freedom (and vice versa); I argue that this view of freedom, while widespread in educational debates today, is overly simplistic. The second approach views freedom as the scope for personal action, which is always supported by social structures and even constraints. I suggest that attention to agency and the structures that promote it brings greater clarity to contemporary discussions of educational freedom, such as student-directed online learning, homeschooling, and increasing regulation.

In each of these examples, I have tried to shift our thinking from freedom *versus* constraint to agency *within* structure. Once we make this conceptual shift, an entirely new type of question opens up: since *all* structures enable certain actions and constrain others, which actions *should* be enabled by educational structures? In other words, what kinds of actions do we want to make sure we enable, even if we do so at the expense of others? It is my contention that conceiving of freedom as agency helps to direct our attention toward precisely these all-important questions.

Notes

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² I use the past tense in this discussion because my focus is on Neill's own description of how Summerhill worked; however, it is worth noting that Summerhill is still in operation today.

³ Illich does not develop an institutional theory in *Deschooling Society*, and so I do not attempt to offer one here. Later in this article I introduce the concept of 'structure', which I take to be broader than 'institution' (i.e., an institution is a particularly formalized manifestation of structure).

⁴ Note that Illich is not opposed to teaching *as such*; rather, he protests the dependence of the learner on institutionally determined learning goals and teacher-packaged instruction.

⁵ For an excellent overview of the roots of structuration theory in earlier debates concerning structure and agency, see Shilling.

⁶ Giddens' account of power clearly reflects the influence of Foucault in arguing that power is *not* "an inherently noxious phenomenon," a unidirectional relation of dominance that social structures could potentially transcend, but rather a multidirectional dynamic enacted by agents in all structures (31-32).

⁷ To be sure, there are many other good criteria besides this one for evaluating educational institutions and regulations. My focus here is on the criterion of students' agency.

⁸ The analysis in this paragraph applies equally to all 'dependent learners' as described by Illich, insofar as they deliberately choose — on the basis of their limited awareness of or access to opportunities for self-teaching — to learn through official schools and teachers.

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